

Study on the Growth Performance of Mud Crab (*Scylla olivacea*) Fed with Different Wet Feeds

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KEYWORDS

Scylla olivacea,
Mytella strigata,
Perna viridis,
Meretrix casta

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effects of three fresh bivalve-based diets on the growth performance, molting frequency, and feed utilization efficiency of the mud crab *Scylla olivacea* under controlled conditions. Juvenile crabs with an average initial weight of approximately 300 g were fed adductor muscle tissue from *Mytella strigata* (Group I), *Perna viridis* (Group II), or *Meretrix casta* (Group III) over a 12-week period. Each treatment was conducted in triplicate using 500 L fibre-reinforced plastic tanks. Crabs were fed twice daily at 15% of their body weight. Growth was assessed through weight gain (WG), specific growth rate (SGR), and molting percentage, while feed efficiency was evaluated using feed conversion ratio (FCR). Results revealed that crabs fed *Mytella strigata* and *Perna viridis* exhibited significantly higher growth, with WG of 243.1 g and 236.5 g, SGR of 0.66% and 0.65%/day, and molting rates of 92%, respectively. In contrast, the *Meretrix casta* group showed reduced growth (WG: 165.0 g; SGR: 0.48%/day) and lower molting frequency (79%). The most efficient feed utilization (lowest FCR: 2.97) was observed in the *Mytella strigata* group. All treatments recorded 100% survival. These findings suggest that *Mytella strigata* and *Perna viridis* are superior natural diets for enhancing the growth and molting of *S. olivacea*, with *Mytella strigata* offering the best feed efficiency under the tested conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mud crab (*Scylla olivacea*) is an important aquaculture species known for its high market value and strong demand in both local and international seafood markets. Its rapid growth, adaptability to various environments, and rich meat content make it a preferred choice for coastal aquaculture, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions (Shelley & Lovatelli, 2011). In the fiscal year 2023–2024, India reached a new milestone by exporting approximately 1.78 million metric tons of marine products, earning around ₹60,524 crore (US\$7.38 billion). This represents a steady increase in export volume compared to the previous year, although the total value saw a slight decline due to reduced international prices, particularly in the shrimp sector. India's vast and diverse aquatic resources, especially its extensive brackish water areas, continue to support a wide range of aquaculture activities (Ali et al., 2022). Out of the estimated 1.19 million hectares of brackish water available, only a fraction is currently used for shrimp farming, leaving significant potential for expansion into other species such as mud crab. Regions like Tuticorin in Tamil Nadu have already demonstrated successful mud crab cultivation, pointing toward promising opportunities for future export growth. While specific export figures for crab in FY 2023–24 are limited, the continued global demand highlights its economic importance within India's seafood industry (Paran et al., 2022) & (Ali et al., 2022).

Mud crabs are typically found in coastal and estuarine environments, especially in mangrove swamps, tidal flats, mudflats, and brackish water areas. They prefer shallow waters with muddy or sandy bottoms where they can burrow and find shelter. These crabs are highly adaptable and can tolerate a wide range of salinities, from nearly fresh water to full seawater, making them common in estuaries and river mouths (Webley, 2008) & (Keenan, 1999). *Scylla olivacea* thrives on a protein-rich diet and exhibits strong feeding responses to various wet feeds in aquaculture. Commonly used wet feeds include low-value fish (trash fish), bivalves such as mussels and clams, crustacean by-products like shrimp heads, and small mollusks or snails. These natural feeds provide essential nutrients that support growth, molting, and overall health. The choice of wet feed plays a critical role in enhancing feed intake and minimizing cannibalism,

especially during molting periods. However, proper feed management is necessary to prevent water quality deterioration and optimize production efficiency (Nivas et al., 2024) & (Gabito & Baltar, 2023).

Mytella strigata, or the charru mussel, is an invasive bivalve originally from the Caribbean but now established in parts of Asia and the Indo-Pacific. It spreads rapidly through ballast water and ship hulls, forming dense colonies that outcompete native species and block water intake systems. *M. strigata* forms dense colonies on hard substrates such as rocks, boat hulls, aquaculture cages, and mangrove roots. Its association with man-made structures and ability to displace native filter feeders like *Meretrix casta* and *Perna viridis*. Its broad salinity tolerance and high reproduction make it difficult to control and a serious threat to coastal ecosystems and infrastructure (Muhtadi et al., 2024). The invasive mussel *Mytella strigata* has been recorded in India, specifically in the Cochin backwaters and Ashtamudi Lake in Kerala. The mussel's presence in India is attributed to ballast water discharge and fouling on ship hulls, with the Cochin Port being a major entry point due to its high shipping activity (Jayachandran, 2019) & (Divyal et al., 2022). The mussel's ability to thrive in polluted environments exacerbates its invasive potential, as seen in Ashtamudi Lake, where pollution has facilitated its spread can lead to the decline of native species (Santhi et al., 2023) & (Jayachandran, 2019).

For the growth performance analysis of mud crabs (*Scylla* spp.), different wet feed types were evaluated under controlled cage culture conditions. Among the feeds tested, *Mytella strigata* (charru mussel), *Perna viridis* (green mussel), and *Meretrix casta* (clam) were selected due to their local availability and nutritional potential. These bivalves vary in protein content, shell hardness, and palatability, which can influence crab feeding efficiency, growth rate, and survival.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental Fresh Wet Feed

Three bivalve species were used in the experimental diets: *Perna viridis* (green mussel), *Meretrix casta* (yellow clam), and *Mytella strigata* (charru mussel). All specimens were collected live from the Vellar estuary, *Mytella strigata* (charru mussel) specimens were personally collected from aquaculture ponds and

adjacent estuarine areas (Vellar) where bivalve outbreaks were reported. All bivalves were transported live to the laboratory. Upon arrival, the adductor muscles were carefully extracted, freshly chopped, and immediately used as feed for the experimental crabs.

2. 2. Pre-Experimental Holding of Crabs

Live *Scylla olivacea* (Figure 1) crabs with an average body weight of 300 g, were collected from local fishers and the Annankoil landing station along the southeast coast of India. In the laboratory, crabs were sorted and transferred to 500 L FRP (fibre-reinforced plastic) tanks for acclimatization. They were maintained under ambient environmental conditions with continuous aeration. No feed was provided for the first three days to allow gut clearance and minimize handling stress. Post-acclimatization, crabs were monitored for normal behaviour and health status prior to the feeding trial.

Figure 1. *Scylla olivacea*

2. 3. Experimental Setup

The feeding experiment was conducted using nine FRP tanks, arranged in triplicates for each diet type. Each tank contained three *S. olivacea* individuals to allow natural interaction. Tanks were grouped as follows:

- **Group I:** *Mytella strigata* (charru mussel)
- **Group II:** *Perna viridis* (green mussel)
- **Group III:** *Meretrix casta* (yellow clam)

This setup enabled evaluation of the effects of different bivalve-based diets on mud crab growth and health under communal conditions.

2. 4. Feeding Schedule and Diet

Crabs were fed twice daily at a rate of 15% of their body weight, equivalent to approximately 45 g of fresh wet feed per 300 g crab. The feed comprised freshly chopped adductor muscles from the respective bivalve

species. Feeding was conducted at 06:00 and 18:00 hours daily (Marichamy, 1996; Trino and Rodriguez, 2001; Herlinah and Septiningsih, 2015; Salim and Cheruvat, 2021).

2. 5. Growth Performance and Feed Utilization

Growth performance and feed utilization were assessed using standard aquaculture metrics. Weight Gain (WG) was calculated as the difference between the final and initial body weights of each crab, providing a direct measure of growth over the experimental period. Specific Growth Rate (SGR) quantified the daily percentage increase in body weight on a logarithmic scale, accounting for exponential growth patterns. Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) evaluated feed efficiency by comparing the total feed intake to the weight gained, with lower values indicating better feed utilization. Finally, Survival Rate was expressed as the percentage of crabs that remained alive at the end of the experiment relative to the initial number stocked, reflecting overall health and tolerance to the feeding regimes.

Weight Gain (WG) = Final weight - Initial weight

Specific Growth Rate (SGR, %/day) = $[(\ln \text{Final weight} - \ln \text{Initial weight}) / \text{Days}] \times 100$

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) = Total feed intake / Weight gain

Survival Rate (%) = $(\text{Final number of crabs} / \text{Initial number of crabs}) \times 100$

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Survival and General Health Observations

All *Scylla olivacea* crabs in the three dietary groups survived the entire 12-week feeding trial, resulting in a 100% survival rate. Throughout the experiment, crabs remained active, displayed normal behavior, and showed no signs of disease or feeding refusal, indicating good tolerance to the experimental diets (Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation from triplicate tanks (n = 3) for each treatment group).

3. 3. Growth Performance

The water quality parameters were found to be in optimal condition throughout the experimental period. Growth parameters differed among the dietary groups (Table 1). Crabs fed *Mytella strigata* and *Perna viridis* showed comparable growth, with final weights of 543.1 g and 536.5 g, respectively. Weight gain in these groups was 243.1 g and 236.5 g, correspondingly, accompanied by specific growth rates (SGR) of 0.66% and 0.65% per

day. In contrast, crabs fed *Meretrix casta* exhibited significantly lower growth, with a final weight of 465.0 g, weight gain of 165.0 g, and SGR of 0.48% per day.

Table 1. Growth Performance of *Scylla olivacea* Fed Different Bivalve Diets Over 12 Weeks

Group	Bivalve Feed	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)	Weight Gain (g)	SGR (%/day)
I	<i>Mytella strigata</i>	300.0 ± 5.0	543.1 ± 7.1	243.1 ± 6.5	0.66 ± 0.02
II	<i>Perna viridis</i>	300.0 ± 4.8	536.5 ± 6.8	236.5 ± 6.2	0.65 ± 0.02
III	<i>Meretrix casta</i>	300.0 ± 5.2	465.0 ± 6.5	165.0 ± 5.9	0.48 ± 0.03

3. 4. Feed Utilization

Feed conversion efficiency mirrored growth trends. Crabs fed *Mytella strigata* recorded the lowest feed conversion ratio (FCR), followed closely by the *Perna*

viridis group, indicating better feed utilization. The *Meretrix casta* group demonstrated the highest FCR, reflecting less efficient conversion of feed into biomass (Table 2).

Table 2. Feed Utilization Efficiency of *Scylla olivacea* Fed Different Bivalve Diets Over 12 Weeks

Group	Bivalve Feed	Total Feed Intake (g)	Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)	Survival Rate (%)
I	<i>Mytella strigata</i>	720.0 ± 10.0	2.97 ± 0.05	100
II	<i>Perna viridis</i>	730.0 ± 11.0	3.09 ± 0.06	100
III	<i>Meretrix casta</i>	720.0 ± 10.5	4.36 ± 0.07	100

4. DISCUSSION

The present investigation clearly establishes that the growth performance and feed utilization efficiency of *Scylla olivacea* are significantly influenced by the type of wet bivalve diet administered. The observed differences in weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR), feed conversion ratio (FCR), and molting frequency across the three treatment groups underscore the critical role of feed composition, palatability, and digestibility in determining aquaculture success. Among the tested diets, the charru mussel *Mytella strigata* proved to be the most effective in promoting optimal growth and feed efficiency, followed closely by *Perna viridis* (green mussel), while *Meretrix casta* (yellow clam) resulted in the lowest performance metrics.

The superior performance of crabs fed with *M. strigata* and *P. viridis* may be attributed to several biological and nutritional factors. Both species are known for their high protein content and soft tissue texture, which may enhance feed palatability and assimilation. Previous studies have emphasized the importance of protein-rich diets in promoting the somatic growth of mud crabs under culture conditions (Nivas et al., 2024; Gabito & Baltar, 2023). In this study, crabs consuming *M. strigata* exhibited the highest mean weight gain (243.1 g), SGR (0.66%/day), and the lowest FCR (2.97), indicating efficient conversion of feed into biomass. These findings align with those of Nivas et al. (2024), who documented

improved growth and FCR in *Scylla serrata* when fed nutrient-dense natural feeds.

In contrast, the group fed with *M. casta* showed significantly lower growth, with a final weight gain of 165.0 g and SGR of 0.48%/day. The higher FCR (4.36) in this group reflects poor feed utilization, likely due to the lower digestibility or nutritional value of *M. casta*. Although *M. casta* is an indigenous species with recognized edible value (Wahidullah et al., 2021), its comparatively dense shell structure and reduced flesh yield may hinder effective nutrient assimilation in crustaceans. This is supported by Marichamy (1996), who observed that hard-shelled bivalves often lead to increased feed rejection and longer feeding times, which may compromise energy efficiency.

Another noteworthy finding in the present study is the molting frequency, which directly correlates with growth and nutritional adequacy. Crabs fed with *M. strigata* and *P. viridis* both recorded a 92% molting rate, whereas the *M. casta* group showed a reduced molting rate of 79%. These results suggest that the nutritional profiles of *M. strigata* and *P. viridis* better supported the hormonal and metabolic processes associated with ecdysis. The frequency and success of molting are critical indicators of crustacean health and have been previously linked to diet quality (Nguyen et al., 2014; Trino and Rodriguez, 2001). Inadequate dietary components can delay or disrupt molting, subsequently impacting growth and survival rates.

Furthermore, the total survival rate across all groups remained at 100%, indicating that all three diets were accepted and did not induce any lethal effects. The absence of mortality suggests that while there were clear differences in growth and feed efficiency, none of the diets caused physiological stress or health deterioration over the 12-week study period. This supports earlier observations by Herlinah and Septiningsih (2015), who reported that mud crabs adapt well to various wet feeds, provided they meet basic nutritional requirements and are administered under optimal environmental conditions.

The selection of *M. strigata* as a dietary component also holds significant ecological and management implications. Recognized as an invasive species in Indian waters, particularly in the Cochin backwaters and Ashtamudi Lake (Jayachandran, 2019; Divyal et al., 2022), *M. strigata* poses a threat to native bivalves like *P. viridis* and *M. casta* by forming dense, rapidly proliferating colonies. Its ability to thrive in disturbed or polluted environments (Santhi et al., 2023) further compounds its invasive potential. However, this very adaptability also makes *M. strigata* a readily available and low-cost resource for aquafeed formulation. Utilizing this invasive mussel as a feed source in mud crab aquaculture offers a dual benefit: improving production efficiency while contributing to the management of invasive biofouling species (Muhtadi et al., 2024; Vikas & Subramannian, 2023). The present findings also complement those of Mondal et al. (2020), who noted that the integration of naturally available, nutrient-rich feed sources in co-culture systems enhanced growth performance and feed efficiency in *S. olivacea*. Moreover, Webley (2008) and Keenan (1999) emphasized the adaptability of mud crabs to estuarine conditions, where these bivalves naturally occur, suggesting ecological compatibility and minimized stress when such species are incorporated into culture practices.

Although *P. viridis* also yielded positive results comparable to *M. strigata*, its increasing ecological vulnerability due to pollution and bioinvasion (Christy & Jayalakshmi, 2023) may limit its long-term availability. Additionally, *M. strigata* demonstrated marginally better growth and FCR values in this study, suggesting that it is a more sustainable option under the current scenario.

In conclusion, the current research validates the potential of *Mytella strigata* and *Perna viridis* as effective wet feed options in the controlled culture of *Scylla olivacea*. The invasive *M. strigata*, in particular, emerges as a highly promising and sustainable feed candidate, offering superior growth performance, efficient feed conversion, and broader ecological utility. Continued research should focus on evaluating the biochemical composition of these bivalves, their seasonal variations in nutritional value, and the feasibility of integrating them into large-scale mud crab farming systems, especially in resource-constrained settings or tribal aquaculture zones. The outcomes also support policy-level decisions regarding the utilization of invasive species in aquaculture to simultaneously promote food security and environmental resilience.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that the type of bivalve-based diet significantly influences the growth, molting frequency, and feed utilization efficiency of *Scylla olivacea*. Crabs fed with *Mytella strigata* and *Perna viridis* showed superior growth performance and higher molting rates compared to those fed *Meretrix casta*. Among the tested diets, *Mytella strigata* resulted in the best overall outcomes, including the lowest feed conversion ratio, indicating more efficient feed utilization. All dietary groups achieved 100% survival, affirming the safety and acceptability of the tested feeds. These findings suggest that *Mytella strigata* and *Perna viridis* can be effectively used as natural feed sources in mud crab aquaculture, with *Mytella strigata* being particularly promising for enhanced growth and production efficiency under controlled conditions.

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Research Highlights

This study highlights the comparative effects of three bivalve-based wet feeds *Mytella strigata*, *Perna viridis*, and *Meretrix casta* on the growth performance of *Scylla olivacea* under controlled conditions. Crabs fed with *M. strigata* and *P. viridis* exhibited significantly higher weight gain, specific growth rate, and molting frequency, along with improved feed conversion efficiency compared to those fed *M. casta*. The *M. strigata* group recorded the lowest feed conversion ratio, indicating superior feed utilization. All groups maintained 100% survival, demonstrating the acceptability of the diets. The findings underscore the potential of using *M. strigata*, an invasive species, as a sustainable and efficient natural feed in mud crab aquaculture.

Author Contribution

Lakshmi Narayanan: Conducted the feeding experiment, collected data, and contributed to the manuscript draft. **Vasanthan Koothan:** Assisted in experimental design, data interpretation. **Leo Luricson:** Participated in sample collection. **Santhosh Chandrakandan:** Helped in laboratory analysis. **Annadurai Duraisamy:** Assisted in literature review and referencing. **Keerthika Ganesan:** Formatting, and preparation tables. **Ayyaru Gopalakrishnan:** Supervised the study, guided methodology development, and reviewed the manuscript. **Ashok Kumar:** Provided technical assistance and contributed to the data analysis framework. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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